

COCOPREND v.1.0

Code of Conduct for Preclinical Neuroimaging Data

Table of contents

Welcome	7
About	9
Background and Goals	9
Core Team	10
Consulting Partners	10
Summary	12
I Basic considerations	15
1 The 3R principles	16
1.1 The Swiss 3R Competence Centre	17
1.2 Swiss 3RCC Network and Partners	17
2 Reproducibility	19
2.1 Terminology	19
3 Open Research Data (ORD)	21
3.1 Research data	21
3.2 Research Data Management (RDM)	21
3.3 Open Research Data (ORD)	22
4 Preregistration	24
4.1 Forms of preregistration	24
4.2 Selected resources	25
5 The FAIR principles	26
5.1 Basic first steps	26
5.2 Summary of FAIR principles	27
5.3 Selected resources	28
6 Data Management Plans (DMPs)	29
6.1 SNSF requirements	29
6.2 General recommendations for DMPs	29
6.3 Selected resources	30

7	Legal & ethical considerations	31
7.1	Legislation	31
7.2	Authorization of animal experiments in Switzerland	32
7.3	Swiss Transparency Agreement on Animal Research (STAAR)	32
7.4	Ethics	33
7.5	Good Laboratory Practices (GLP)	33
II	Data Organization and Metadata	34
8	Standards	35
8.1	Finding data structure standards	35
8.2	Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS)	35
8.3	The Open Microscopy Environment (OME) and related standards	36
9	Documentation, protocols and reporting	37
9.1	Readme files	37
9.2	Documenting data collection	38
9.3	Reporting guidelines: ARRIVE	40
10	Tables and spreadsheets	43
10.1	Organizing tables or spreadsheets	43
10.2	Frequent actions with tables	45
11	Metadata companion files	48
11.1	Format: JavaScript Object Notation (JSON)	48
11.2	Creating metadata files from tables	49
12	Controlled vocabularies and ontologies	51
12.1	Controlled vocabularies	51
12.2	Taxonomies	51
12.3	Ontologies	52
12.4	Selected resources	52
III	Archiving, Sharing and Publishing	53
13	File formats	54
13.1	File formats in the general domain	54
13.2	Interoperable formats in neuroimaging	55
13.3	Metadata, markup and data serialization	57
13.4	File format conversion	57
14	Version control	58
14.1	Version control in documents	58

14.2 Git version control system for data science	59
14.3 Selected resources	64
15 Archives and online repositories	65
15.1 Types of data archives	65
15.2 Open Research Data (ORD) online repositories	66
References	69
IV Appendix	72
Glossary	73
R Code examples	81
R code snippets for table manipulation	81
R code snippet to create JSON files from a table	82

List of Figures

2.1	Definitions of reproducibility from The Turing Way	20
3.1	Research data life cycle according to RDMkit by ELIXIR, 2021-2024	22
14.1	Centralized vs distributed version control systems	59
14.2	Overview of Git commands	61
14.3	Illustration of git branches from the Turing Way	62

List of Tables

1.1	The 3R principles for more humane animal research	16
1.2	Swiss 3RCC partners	17
10.1	A poorly formatted table	45
10.2	A table formatted for machine-readability	45
10.3	Example of a codebook	46
10.4	A table in wide format	47
10.5	Table converted to long format	47
11.1	Example of metadata in tabular format.	50
15.1	An overview of different types of data archives depending on the frequency of access.	65
15.2	Table with file information	82
15.3	Combined table after adding subject information	82

Welcome

COCOPREND compiles and distills resources to facilitate **responsible** and **ethical use, sharing and management of preclinical (animal) neuroimaging data**. This data code of conduct is elaborated by the [Center for Reproducible Science \(CRS\)](#) of the University of Zurich. This website is meant to be a **living document** that is regularly edited and updated by the community.

This project is funded by the [Swiss Academies of Arts and Sciences \(a+\)](#) as part of the Action line D2.6 call of the Open Research Data (ORD) action plan. The funding period is 01.10.2024 to 30.06.2025.

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About

This project is funded by the [Swiss Academies of Arts and Sciences \(a+\)](#) as part of the Action line D2.6. The codes of conduct sought by this call should serve as guiding principles to ensure the responsible and ethical use, sharing, and management of research data for different disciplines or specific data communities.

COCOPREND is conducted by the [Center for Reproducible Science \(CRS\)](#).

Funding period: 01.10.2024 - 30.06.2025

Background and Goals

Despite large volumes of data being generated in preclinical neuroimaging research, there is a lack of adequate support for processing them according to the [FAIR](#) (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles. This gap leads to inefficient data management and limited utility of the data that are made openly available. This project aims to develop a conduct for open research data (ORD) specifically targeting researchers working with **preclinical (animal) neuroimaging data**. The target community includes researchers using various imaging techniques to study the central nervous system in animals. In particular, this code of conduct provides resources for researchers active in Switzerland.

While there are comprehensive guidelines for planning, conducting and reporting animal experiments, as well as for managing data of different imaging modalities, the landscape of these resources is fragmented. This project systematically compiles and distills these resources to facilitate adoption of FAIR ORD practices by researchers. This code of conduct is developed **collaboratively** by the Center for Reproducible Science and key stakeholders including animal neuroscientists.

This code of conduct will benefit the [3R](#) principles (Replacement, Reduction, Refinement) in animal research and improve **data reusability** and harmonisation in the community.

Core Team

The code of conduct is developed at the University of Zurich (UZH), Center for Reproducible Science (CRS).

- **Dr. Gorka Fraga González** (main scientist). Role: Main contributor to the tasks of elaborating and disseminating the code of conduct. Expertise: He is co-leading the project [AFFORD: A framework for avoiding the open research data dump](#) which involves data support to several groups of the target community. Experienced with multiple imaging techniques, he is involved in the elaboration of ORD guidelines and data stewardship.
- **Fabio Molo** (project manager), managing director of CRS. Role: Project supervision and coordination, review and editing. Expertise: Fabio Molo is the managing director of the CRS, involved in research and teaching at the center and focused on open and reproducible research practices.
- **Prof. Dr. Leonhard Held** (consulting senior scientist). Role: Link to Swiss Reproducibility Network, to the CRS community, and to institutional bodies at the University of Zurich. Expertise: Leonhard Held is head of the UZH biostatistics department, chair of the steering committee of the CRS, and co-PI of the project AFFORD which involves the target research community. He is a member of the Task Force on ORD in the Health and Life Sciences, mandated by the [ORD Strategy Council](#), and a founding steering committee member of the [Swiss Reproducibility Network](#). He is committed to ensuring transparency and reproducibility of research through Open Data and Open Code.

Consulting Partners

The following consulting partners will be involved in disseminating the code of conduct and will act as interface with the target community.

- **Prof. Dr. Vartan Kurtcuoglu**. Role: interface between target research community and the CRS. Expertise: Domain-specific expertise. Vartan Kurtcuoglu is the head of the [The Interface Group](#) at the Institute of Physiology, with the mission to address clinical needs through the convergence of engineering, biological and medical research.
- **PD Dr. Dr. Benjamin Ineichen**. Role: interface between target research community and the CRS. Expertise: expertise in preclinical neuroimaging and 3R. Junior group leader of the [STRIDE lab](#) with the vision to bridge the gap between preclinical and clinical research.

- **Dr. Paulin Jirkof.** Role: interface between target research community and the CRS. Expertise: Domain-specific expertise. 3R coordinator for the University of Zurich since 2018 and representative of the University of Zurich as node coordinator at the [Swiss 3RCC](#), board member of the Swiss Laboratory Animal Science Association.

Summary

This code of conduct compiles existing guidelines for planning, conducting and reporting animal experiments and distills them into key recommendations, in the legal and institutional context in Switzerland. The main focus is on enabling researchers to produce research data than can be reused by others.

Each chapter begins with a concise recommendation on the topic, followed by conceptual clarifications, a selection of relevant resources, and/or more specific practical tips. The appendix contains a glossary of the key terms per chapter.

Part I Basic considerations

We begin by introducing basic concepts and definitions: the 3R principles of replacement, reduction and refinement; different aspects of reproducibility; the FAIR principles and open research data; how preregistration and data management plans can contribute to reproducibility and the 3R principles; and relevant legal and ethical frameworks in Switzerland. *Key recommendations* in this area are:

- Apply the principles of **Replacement, Reduction, and Refinement** to all experimental design and data practices. Refer to Swiss 3RCC and partners for 3R tools and guidance.
- Manage research data *as if* it would become of **public** domain.
- **Document** data in a way that it can or could be reused by researchers outside your group.
- **Share all metadata** and, whenever possible, also all data.
- Consider routinely **preregistering** every experiment and analysis.
- Aim for a **realistic** degree of **FAIRness** in your data, depending on the available resources and required capabilities.
- Use **data management plans** as a living, editable document to guide data management in a project. Use version control and track changes in this document.
- Consult a **data steward** for assistance in writing and implementing a data management plan.
- Consider the relevant **legal and ethical guidelines** already *before* starting your research project.

Part II Data Organization and Metadata

The second part describes how to find and use discipline-specific standards for organizing and documenting data and metadata and provides practical guidance on working with tables and spreadsheets, metadata companion files and controlled vocabularies. *Key recommendations* in this area are:

- Adopt data and metadata **standards** that are actively maintained and used by a broad community.
- If no established standard is available, **adapt** an existing standard rather than create a new one.
- Produce **documentation** that can be understood by collaborators outside your group **as early as possible**.
- Utilize the wide range of existing **templates** as well as discipline-specific **reporting guidelines**.
- Structure and format the tables so that they can be **machine-readable**.
- Use **interoperable file formats**.
- Include a **data dictionary** describing the data.
- Always keep the raw data and keep **track of changes**.
- Plan the content of **metadata companion files** early on and follow standards when available. Automate the generation of these files.
- Adopt a **controlled vocabulary**, and consider adopting more complex structures like taxonomies or ontologies.

Part III Archiving, Sharing and Publishing

The third part describes how to choose file formats and use version control for the purpose of archiving, sharing and publishing data, and introduces different types of data archives and online repositories available for research data. *Key recommendations* in this area are:

- Prioritize **long-term sustainability** and interoperability when choosing file format.
- Use formats widely used in your data **community**.
- Use **Git for version control** when producing research code, and consider its use also for other text data and metadata tables and files.
- Begin with **simple workflows** without trying to utilize all the advance features from the start.
- Plan ahead for **archiving** research outputs, defining what, how, when, and where.

- Treat **metadata and documentation** with the same importance as the data itself.

Part I

Basic considerations

1 The 3R principles

The principles of the 3Rs concerning animal experimentation were postulated in 1959 by William Russell and Rex Burch in a book entitled *Principles of Humane Experimental Technique*. The principles are today internationally widely recognized by scientists as a moral obligation. They are moreover implemented in many national legislations on animal protection.

We recommend using these principles and associated resources as guidance to improve research data management. Generating reusable data will help **reduce research waste** and maximize the **utility** of animal experiments.

Table 1.1: The 3R principles for more humane animal research

Principle	Description	Details
Replacement	Methods that achieve a purpose without conducting experiments or procedures on animals.	Approaches that do not use living animals, such as cultured cells, tissues, organs, and in silico computational methods. Use of animals that are not considered capable of experiencing suffering, such as some invertebrates and immature vertebrates.
Reduction	Methods that obtain comparable information using fewer animals or maximize data collection from the same number of animals.	Reduction strategies include: Optimization of breeding programs, experimental design, and statistical analysis. Sharing animal materials (organs, tissues, cells). Using longitudinal instead of cross-sectional measurements. Reducing unexplained variation in data

Principle	Description	Details
Refinement	Methods that minimize pain, suffering, and distress while enhancing animal well-being.	Improving housing, handling, anesthesia, and analgesia. Habituation to procedures and execution of humane endpoints. Developing better tools to assess suffering and well-being.

1.1 The Swiss 3R Competence Centre

The Swiss 3R Competence Centre [swiss3RCC](#) is a national center that promotes research, education and communication for the replacement, reduction and refinement of animal experimentation (3Rs principle).

Use their website as a **hub** to find the most important resources related to the 3R principles. Their activities include:

- Funding of projects and initiatives advancing 3R principles.
- Education & training.
- Sharing knowledge on best practices for animal welfare.
- Events promoting animal welfare in research.
- Awards to recognize contributions to the 3Rs.
- Research & resources to promotes development of 3Rs methods.

1.2 Swiss 3RCC Network and Partners

The Swiss 3RCC partners are listed in Table 1.2. More information on the extended network including observer members, 3Rs centers and international partners can be found in their website: <https://swiss3rcc.org/network-and-partners>.

Table 1.2: Swiss 3RCC partners

Swiss Partners

[Animalfree Research](#)
[Animal Research Tomorrow \(ART\)](#)

Swiss Partners

Ethics Committee for Animal Experimentation (ECAE)
Federal Ethics Committee on Non-Human Biotechnology (ECNH)
Institute für Labortierkunde, University of Zurich (LTK)
National Research Programme NRP 79 Advancing 3R
Réseau des Animaleries Lémaniques (RESAL)
Swiss Academies of Arts and Sciences
Swiss Academy of Sciences
Swiss Animal Welfare Officer Network AWO-N
Swiss Animal Facilities Network SAFN
Swiss Laboratory Animal Sciences Association (SGV)
Swiss National Science Foundation
Swissuniversities
Swiss Association of Veterinarians in Industry and Research (SAVIR)
LS2 Life Sciences Switzerland

2 Reproducibility

One goal of good research data management is to improve the **reproducibility of scientific findings**, which is crucial for the trustworthiness of empirical research. This code of conduct discusses important steps towards improving reproducibility, such as adopting standards for organising data, providing documentation and metadata, and using interoperable file formats, controlled vocabularies, and version control. Throughout, the code will refer to different aspects of reproducibility, which we introduce in this chapter. Irrespective of exact definitions, we recommend researchers consider scientific reproducibility to be a **continuum** that benefits from any action and effort that improves transparency and reusability of their research outputs.

“Science is widely regarded as the most reliable way of turning observations into facts. But none of our scientific facts should be based on a single study, or one set of results. Whenever a study claims to have made a new discovery, it is the job of science to ask how we can verify and confirm these results.” (Held and Schwab 2020).

2.1 Terminology

2.1.1 (2019) Definitions by the US National Academy of Sciences

The [National Academy of Sciences](#) discussed the following concepts in their 2019 book on scientific reproducibility and replicability (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering and Medicine 2019):

- **Reproducibility or computational reproducibility:** obtaining consistent computational results using the same input data, computational steps, methods, code, and conditions of analysis;
- **Replicability:** obtaining consistent results across studies aimed at answering the same scientific question, each of which has obtained its own data.
- **Generalizability:** refers to the extent that results of a study apply in other contexts or populations that differ from the original one.

A single scientific study may entail one or more of these concepts.

2.1.2 (2022) Definitions by the Turing Way

The Turing way book (The Turing Way Community 2022) added the concept of ‘robustness’ and systematized the different aspects of reproducibility in the matrix shown in Figure 2.1.

		Data	
		Same	Different
Analysis	Same	Reproducible	Replicable
	Different	Robust	Generalisable

Figure 2.1: Definitions of reproducibility from The Turing Way

2.1.3 (2023) Definitions by the iRISE project

The EU-funded project [iRISE - improving Reproducibility In Science - Open Knowledge Base](#), in its [glossary](#), highlights another aspect of reproducibility, which links the concept to open science practices: ‘the extent to which design, implementation, analysis, and reporting of a study enable a third party to repeat the study and assess its findings’. We recommend the iRISE glossary as a resource for those interested in recent in-depth discussion of the terminology around reproducibility. In this code of conduct we will use the earlier terminology from the Turing Way as it is standard and established in various areas of empirical research.

3 Open Research Data (ORD)

We recommend handling research data through its life cycle *as if* it would become of public domain. Even if, for legal, ethical or other reasons the data cannot be made accessible to everyone without restrictions, the metadata describing the data can, almost always, be shared openly. This means managing research data with a focus on its external reusability, that is, with enough documentation to enable reuse by external collaborators outside one's own research group. To achieve this, it is important to first understand what is meant by research data, the differences between research data management and open research data, and the different stages of the data life cycle.

3.1 Research data

According to the [Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development \(OECD\)](#) (source from 2021) **research data** from public funding includes:

(...) actual records (such as numerical scores, textual records, images, and sounds) resulting from research that is partially or fully funded by public funds, used as primary sources for scientific research, and that are commonly accepted in the scientific community as necessary to validate research findings. This term does not cover laboratory notebooks, preliminary analyses, or drafts of scientific papers, plans for future research, peer reviews, personal communications with colleagues, or physical objects, (e.g., laboratory samples, strains of bacteria, or test animals).

3.2 Research Data Management (RDM)

RDM can be defined as

(...) the handling of research data (collection, organisation, storage, and documentation) during and after a research activity. (<https://www.scienceurope.org/our-priorities/open-science/research-data-management>).

It is often conceptualized with reference to the **research data life cycle** illustrated in Figure 3.1. RDM is therefore a generic term that doesn't necessarily imply open access to research data or alignment with best practices. For instance, RDM could be interpreted to refer to managing data internally without the curation efforts to make it reusable when shared.

Figure 3.1: Research data life cycle according to [RDMkit](#) by ELIXIR, 2021-2024

3.3 Open Research Data (ORD)

ORD can be defined as

Data that can be freely accessed, reused, remixed and redistributed, for academic research and teaching purposes and beyond. Ideally, open data have no restrictions on reuse or redistribution, and are appropriately licensed as such ([Open Science Training Handbook](#)).

This definition focuses on **open licensing** and the absence of technical access barriers. In praxis, however, “openness” also implies a broader sense of accessibility, including things such as comprehensive documentation and metadata that are an essential prerequisite of any public sharing of research data.

Producing ORD is also **required in SNSF funded projects** (see [SNSF policy on ORD](#)). This policy follows the statement “*research data are the evidence that underpins the answer to the research question, and can be used to validate findings regardless of its form (e.g. print, digital, or physical).*” from the [Concordat on Open Research Data](#). In addition, since 2017 the SNSF requires to have a Data Management Plan (DMP) outlining the data life cycle, including where and how they will be shared and preserved

(cf. [research policies](#)). Other funders such as the European Union (Horizon Europe) make similar requirements (cf. [open aire requirements](#)).

The recent project **recORD - recognise Open Research Data practices**, with a focus on research assessment, acknowledged that ORD practices should take into account that “open”, and even “data”, are terms that can have different meanings across disciplines and epistemic cultures (Araujo, Bornatici, and Heers 2024). In the recORD project, practices are defined as integral components of the broader concept of **open science**. These practices are defined as

(...)practices aimed at facilitating access to and reuse of research data by any interested party, contingent upon specific agreements based on the type of data (Fecher and Friesike 2014).

4 Preregistration

A preregistration specifies the research questions and the analysis plan before conducting the study. As such it allows to clearly distinguish the testing of a hypothesis with new data from the generation of hypotheses with existing observations, making research more robust, replicable and transparent (Nosek et al. 2018).

Preregistering a study does not imply that you cannot conduct any additional exploratory analyses or change plans after data are collected. It will merely clarify the differences between analyses decided a priori and those decided after looking at the data. If a publication derives from a preregistered study, which is common, it is important to disclose and justify the changes transparently in the manuscript.

Preregistration has some additional benefits:

- Preregistration can prevent unnecessary repetition of animal studies since it promotes systematic search of preceding studies and helps formulating relevant research questions.
- Much of the information included in a preregistration is often required for ethical approval, so the effort investing in elaborating a preregistration can be relatively low. In fact, having a well-defined analysis plan can facilitate the analytic decision process and save time in later stages of a research project.

We recommend adopting one of the preregistration forms listed below. The simplest option, such as a minimal template for a preregistered research plan, is a good starting point.

4.1 Forms of preregistration

- **Preregistration.** Consists in registering a research plan (hypotheses, methods, analyses) before an study is conducted. A preregistration does not necessarily have to be public, as long as it is registered and time-stamped on a trusted platform. Read more on <https://www.cos.io/initiatives/prereg>.
- **Registered reports.** Involve a two-stage peer review process where a study proposal is reviewed before data collection and the final manuscript is reviewed after analysis. At stage 1, researchers can obtain in-principle acceptance, so even if no statistically significant results are found in the planned analyses, the paper

would be accepted for publication. Read more on <https://www.cos.io/initiatives/registered-reports> and in Hardwicke and Ioannidis (2018).

- **Peer community in registered reports (PCI-RR).** The PCI initiative is a researcher-run initiative that publishes peer-reviews of preprints and the PCI-RR community is dedicated to receiving, reviewing and recommending registered reports across disciplines. Read more on this topic and find a list of PCI-RR friendly journals on <https://rr.peercommunityin.org/about/>

4.2 Selected resources

- **Open Science Framework** is a platform where you can upload and create project registration and preregistrations. It has a variety of **templates** in multiple formats.
- **As predicted.** A platform to facilitate preregistration, with a focus on using very simple and easy to fill in questionnaire. Answering the simple questions ([see this sample](#)) of the questionnaire will generate a time-stamped single page .pdf document with a unique URL for verification. You cannot import templates from other preregistration platforms into AsPredicted but you can use the document from AsPredicted in other platforms (e.g., OSF).
- **Preclinical EU.** A platform aimed at providing a comprehensive data base of pre-clinical animal study protocols. Studies can be registered anonymously, free of charge and with an optional embargo period. Its adoption after 3 years was evaluated in a report Van Der Naald et al. (2022).
- **Animal registry.** An online registry for scientific studies involving animals conducted around the world.
- **Animal welfare science template.** Adapted from the Open Science Framework's generic preregistration template. It highlights and gives examples relevant to animal welfare research. Developed as part of the COST action Lifting Farm Animal Lives (**LIFT**).

5 The FAIR principles

The [FAIR principles](#) of **Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability** (Wilkinson et al. 2016), are the most widely adopted framework for guiding the management of digital resources, in particular, scientific data and metadata. They define guiding principles and practices intended to enable both machines and humans to reuse research data. These core precepts have led to a myriad of guidelines and initiatives to define, evaluate and implement them in practice. We endorse the flexible FAIRification framework (Welter et al. 2023) that emphasizes three key practical aspects: setting realistic, incremental goals; tailoring support to the individual needs; and working in multidisciplinary teams, involving all scientific and infrastructure stakeholders relevant to the individual project.

We recommend to follow a flexible approach aiming for a balanced “FAIR enough” status of the data, depending on the available resources and required capabilities.

5.1 Basic first steps

Caution

Many of the references and resources for data FAIRification are written for data engineers or data stewards and can be too technical for researchers from outside that domain. However, all researchers from any field have the responsibility of documenting their protocols and producing adequately formatted metadata. This is essential for transparency and scientific reproducibility, and the starting point for generating reusable data.

Each FAIR principle has subprinciples with definitions that may slightly vary depending on the field. FAIRification is a process with the ultimate goal of making our data become *machine actionable* digital objects. That is not always achievable and requires many resources. However, at a minimum, researchers can aim at producing metadata that is human and machine-readable to a degree sufficient to enable experts to reuse their data without requiring unreasonable efforts to understand it. FAIR does not necessarily mean the data will be open and publicly available. Thus, as a starting point, we consider that a research must:

1. provide sufficient machine-readable **metadata** or context to their data

2. share or publish the data in **repositories** that are **FAIR-compatible** to a reasonable degree (e.g., provide persistent identifiers and require metadata).

5.2 Summary of FAIR principles

FAIR Principle	Description
Findable	It should be possible for others to discover your data. Rich metadata should be available online in a searchable resource, and the data should be assigned a persistent identifier.
F1	(Meta)data are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers.
F2	Data are described with rich metadata.
F3	Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe.
F4	(Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.
Accessible	It should be possible for humans and machines to gain access to your data, under specific conditions or restrictions where appropriate. FAIR does not mean that data need to be open! There should be metadata, even if the data are not accessible.
A1	(Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communication protocol.
A1.1	The protocol is open, free and universally implementable.
A1.2	The protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure where necessary.
A2	Metadata should be accessible even when the data is no longer available.
Interoperable	Data and metadata should conform to recognized formats and standards to allow them to be combined and exchanged.
I1	(Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
I2	(Meta)data use vocabularies that follow the FAIR principles.
I3	(Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data.
Reusable	Lots of documentation is needed to support data interpretation and reuse. The data should conform to community norms and be clearly licensed so others know what kinds of reuse are permitted.

FAIR Principle	Description
R1	(Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.
R1.1	(Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license.
R1.2	(Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance.
R1.3	(Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards.

5.3 Selected resources

- [FAIR data page](#) from the library of the University of Zurich. It includes tutorial and checklists.
- [FAIR checker](#) is a webapp to help you improve your metadata and inspect metadata of published data. Just add the URL of a dataset. It will give a 'FAIRness' score and describe how much each FAIR principle is fulfilled.

6 Data Management Plans (DMPs)

We recommend using a data management plan (DMP) as a living document to guide research data management in a project. Besides fulfilling the requirements from the funding agencies for data sharing and publishing, DMPs can be very useful tools to improve efficiency of our research workflow.

6.1 SNSF requirements

The SNSF **requires** a DMP for approved applications (see [SNSF guidelines](#)). A DMP should give information on the data life cycle. The minimum structure and content that a DMP should provide are shown in the SNSF's [DMP form](#). The form includes four sections:

1. Data collection and documentation
2. Ethics, legal and security issues
3. Data storage and preservation
4. Data sharing and reuse.

The **DMP remains editable** during the entire lifetime of the grant. Its contents can be adapted as the project evolves. Thus, it is recommended to tracking changes and keep control of the versions of this document.

The DMP content can be relatively broad and they are very individual. DMPs should be **plausible, suit their project** and meet **standards by the research community**.

6.2 General recommendations for DMPs

Our recommendations are the following:

- Use SNSF form-based **templates** when available.

- Include enough **details** so that this document can accompany the project and be useful to conduct the data-related actions at different stages of the data life cycle (see [Open Research Data](#)). A DMP can be a very useful tool **for project management**.
- **Update it** when changes or deviations from the original plans are needed.
- Use **version control** and track changes.
- **Share it** with collaborators. Within a project, it can be used as an onboarding document and as a sort of project blueprint. When shared outside a project, it can help communities to adopt similar standards and facilitate collaboration and data reuse.
- Consult a **data steward** for inputs when writing a DMP. A data steward or someone in a similar role can help finding DMPs from similar fields, choosing community standards, assessing project's needs regarding data management and reviewing the DMP's content so that it is sufficiently detailed

6.3 Selected resources

Type	Description
Examples	DMP examples from UK's Digital Curation Center
Examples	DMP examples by the University of Bern
Generator	DMP generator by Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics. It has predefined boxes that will generate a doc with predefined paragraphs. Requires Switch Edu-ID login. Oriented for life sciences
Form	SNSF form for DMPs (link to pdf)
Form	DMP Data Life-Cycle Management (DLCM) project: form based on SNSF's template
Checklist	Data Life-Cycle Management (DLCM) project: DMP checklist
Templates	École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL) DMP template - link to pdf

7 Legal & ethical considerations

There are many legal and ethical aspects to responsible preclinical research. This chapter lists important resources, in particular relating to the situation in Switzerland. We recommend consulting the relevant guidelines early, ideally in the planning phase of a project. Also, whenever possible, we recommend following any standard for transparency agreements and lab procedures. We suggest considering such frameworks as resources enshrining expert and societal consensus on responsible research.

7.1 Legislation

In Switzerland, the «dignity of living beings» has been enshrined in the **Federal Constitution** ([Art. 120 para. 2](#)) since 1992, and the «dignity of animals» in the **Animal Welfare Act** ([Art. 1 in conjunction with Art. 3 let. a](#)) since 2008. For more details, consult the [regulatory framework summary](#) by Swissuniversities.

7.1.1 Laws and ordinances

- **Animal Welfare Act** ([AniWA; 455](#))
 - Protects animal dignity and ensures animal welfare.
- **Ordinance on Animal Protection** ([TSchV/OPAn; 455.1](#))
 - Defines rules on animal handling, use, and housing.
 - Regulates how interventions are performed on animals (e.g., authorized and forbidden procedures, analgesia, housing infrastructure requirements).
- **Animal Experimentation Ordinance** ([AEO; 455.163](#))
 - Defines rules on laboratory animal breeding.
 - Regulates genetically modified animals.
 - Specifies requirements for laboratory animal breeding announcements and animal experimentation.
- **Animal Welfare Training Ordinance** ([AWTO; 455.109.1](#))
 - Defines the basic education needed for persons working with animals.
 - Establishes content and minimal duration of education and training courses.

- Specifies requisite continuing education for persons working with animals.
- **Ordinance on Electronic Management of Animal Experiments** ([VerTiV/O-SIGEXPA; 455.61](#))
 - Regulates the operation of the management information system for animal experimentation.
 - Covers reports, basic training, and continuing education certificates.
- **Containment Ordinance** ([ContainO 814.912](#))
 - Regulates “the handling of organisms, in particular genetically modified, pathogenic or alien organisms, in contained systems.”

7.2 Authorization of animal experiments in Switzerland

The [AniWA](#) stipulates that every animal experiment and the keeping of laboratory animals in Switzerland **must be authorised**.

A **weighing of interests** is carried out for each application. Applicants need to consider **ethical** as well as **scientific** aspects. The expected gain in knowledge is weighed against the burden on the animals to keep the number of animals as low as possible, to protect the animals from excessive stress and to define appropriate termination criteria. In addition, those conducting experiments are obliged to report the number of times they have used laboratory animals and to report on completed experiments.

The **Ethics Committee for Animal Experimentation** ([ECAE](#)) of the Swiss Academies has published an extensive guideline to help researchers carry out the weighing of interests for any proposed animal experiment ([2nd Edition from 2022](#)).

7.3 Swiss Transparency Agreement on Animal Research (STAAR)

Swissuniversities has set up the [STAAR Commission](#) to improve communication and transparency regarding the use of animals in research. The signatory organizations agree to the following [commitments](#)):

- We will be clear about how and why we use or support the use of animals in research,
- We will enhance our communication with the public and the media about our involvement with research using animals,
- We will be proactive in providing opportunities for the public to find out about our involvement with research using animals,

- We will report on progress annually and share our experiences

The specific objectives of STAAR are defined each year (see [STAAR standards](#)).

7.4 Ethics

- [Ethics Committee for Animal Experimentation](#)
 - Developed principles and guidelines: *Ethical principles and guidelines for experiments on animals*.
 - Created the guidance: *Weighing of interests for proposed animal experiments. Guidance for applicants*.
- [Dignity of the Animal Study Group \(FSVO\)](#)
 - Devised a model procedure to ensure that weighing of interests is carried out correctly and uniformly.

7.5 Good Laboratory Practices (GLP)

The goal of GLPs is to ensure quality of the process and conditions under which studies are planned, performed, monitored, recorded, archived and reported.

Animal tests carried out in accordance with GLP for chemicals, therapeutic products (human and animal), plant protection products and biocidal products in Switzerland are internationally recognised. This means that the tests do not have to be repeated for each country, thus unnecessary animal tests can be avoided (principle of *reduction*).

- There is a **Swiss Federal ordinance on GLPs**: [813.112.1 Ordinance of 18 May 2005 on Good Laboratory Practice \(OGLP\)](#)

Other relevant GLP authorities are:

- **Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)** (see [OECD Series on Principles of GLP and compliance monitoring](#))
- **U.S. Food and Drug Administration (US-FDA)**. See [GLP for nonclinical laboratory studies](#))
- **European Medicines Agency (EMA)**

Part II

Data Organization and Metadata

8 Standards

There are many field and community-specific **standards** describing how to **structure data and metadata, filenaming conventions and file formats**. We recommend searching for what is available, reusing it or modifying it just as much as necessary. Adopting available community standards will result in a much lower workload than defining a new standard from scratch. We recommend adopting standards that are actively maintained, well documented and that are used by a broad community for some time. If no standard is available for a specific data type or community, it is preferable to adapt standards for similar data types than to create a new one. Some popular standards offer the possibility of submitting extension proposals for additional data types.

8.1 Finding data structure standards

Data stewards or researchers involved in planning data management may need to conduct a systematic search for field-specific metadata standards.

- The FAIRsharing (<https://fairsharing.org/>) resource is an extensive list of data and metadata standards, databases, and policies, and it is kept up-to-date by the field-specific research communities (Sansone et al. 2019).
- The Digital Curation center of the UK also offers a list of metadata standards organized by discipline: <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/guidance/standards/metadata>

8.2 Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS)

The [Brain Imaging Data Structure \(BIDS\)](#) (Gorgolewski et al. 2016) describes a series of data organization principles to facilitate **large-scale data sharing** between researchers, while also making metadata **machine-readable** to allow automation. It started in 2015 and it can be considered one of the most complete guidelines in neuroimaging. It covers a range of imaging modalities (MRI, EEG, iEEG, MEG, PET, CT, microscopy). Although initially focused on human data it has ongoing extension developments **related to animal research data**. Since 2020, the [BEP032](#) project has been developing a proposal for animal electrophysiology and associated tools. The [BIDS extension proposals](#)

(BEP) process allows researchers to propose BIDS specifications for their data modality, which are then reviewed and integrated into the standards. BIDS guidelines cover multiple aspects of data management including:

- Data structure
- Metadata
- File names and formats
- Preprocessing and analysis workflows

The defining features of BIDS are those desirable in most standards:

- **Flexible and easy-to-adopt.** BIDS combines technically complex documentation with more accessible guides and apps to facilitate adherence, particularly for early-career researchers. The BIDS Starter Kit collects tutorials, wikis, and templates to help any lab get started with BIDS.
- **Community-driven, platform-independent, and growing.** BIDS was developed by researchers and it has evolved from its initial focus on human functional magnetic resonance imaging to accommodate other data modalities (EEG, MEG, PET, CT, microscopy).
- **An ecosystem of resources.** BIDS has fostered an ecosystem of tools and resources, including validation tools, apps for data preprocessing, and databases like [OpenNeuro](#).

8.3 The Open Microscopy Environment (OME) and related standards

The Open Microscopy Environment (OME; <https://www.openmicroscopy.org/>) is a consortium of universities, research labs, industry and developers producing open-source software and format standards for microscopy data. It was established in 2005 and remains very active. OME has its own collection of standards listed in the FAIRsharing platform: <https://fairsharing.org/OME>.

The different microscopy techniques and image modalities have led to multiple initiatives to create specific standards built on or extend the OME data model (Goldberg et al. 2005). Some of these community-extensions are discussed in Ropelewski et al. (2022) and (Sarkans et al. 2021). There is also an active BIDS extension for microscopy data (Bourget et al. 2022).

9 Documentation, protocols and reporting

Documentation is metadata, that is, information about our data objects, mostly aimed at human readers and usually consisting of text and images. We recommend producing useful documentation from early on and through out the entire project. It should preferably be written in a way that can be understood by other collaborators from the start, to prevent additional efforts translating internal documentation into more publishable documents. We also recommend using discipline-specific guidelines when available, to reduce efforts and to facilitate reuse by others in the community.

9.1 Readme files

README files are text files usually written in text (.txt) or Markdown (.md) formats. They are intended for humans rather than for machine-readability. It is good practice to have at least a README file at the root directory (the topmost folder) of a project folder or code repository. They are usually concise and can be placed at multiple levels. For example, at the project-level providing information about the the project authors, institution, goals, etc. At data-level, they can provide information about the data sets and help users navigate the folder or perform actions. When accessing a code repository in Gitlab or Github, the user is presented with the content of a README file that provides the main instructions and information about the repository.

An example of the content in a README file based on https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/metadata_management:

```
PROJECT TITLE
- Project Unique ID
- Funding Grant Nr and period
- Description: <provide a short description of the study/project>
- Principle Investigator:
- Data contact person
- Link to Data management plan

ORGANIZATION <in large projects, this can also describe subfolders>
- Folder structure
- File naming conventions (with examples)
- File formats
```

9.2 Documenting data collection

Data collection is the basis for research findings. Procedures and quality measures need to be implemented and documented to have reliable data.

9.2.1 Key considerations

As described in <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/collecting> :

- Capture the provenance e.g. of samples, researchers and instruments.
- Ensure data quality, since data can either be generated by yourself, or by another infrastructure or facility with this specialisation.
- Check options for reusing data instead of generating new data.
- Define the experimental design including a collection plan (e.g. repetitions, controls, randomisation) in advance.
- Calibrate the instruments.
- Check data protection and security issues if you work with sensitive or confidential data.
- Define how to store the data e.g. format and volume.
- Find suitable repository to store the data.
- Identify suitable metadata standards.

9.2.2 Tools for data management and documentation during data collection

It is necessary to document what happens in the lab in an **electronic** format, with **version control** and **tracked changes**. If handwritten notes cannot be avoided, they should be digitized in an interoperable format as soon as possible. Suitable tools are:

- Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELNs)
- Electronic Data Capture (EDC) systems
- Laboratory Information Management Systems (LIMS)

Some of these tools can be complex, expensive and have a broader scope, integrating workflows for analysis and file storage. Research groups need to find a balance between their needs and available resources (financial or in user expertise) to choose one.

Researchers should also consider:

- Long-term sustainability of the tools (e.g., is the tool likely to be maintained in the long run?)
- Dependencies (e.g., do researchers need a lot of technical support from external organizations? Are they accessible?)
- Format lock-in (e.g., the tool should allow exporting data into a format that can be imported into other platforms without losing information)
- Scalability (e.g., can it be adapted to new lab collaborators?)
- Portability (e.g., how easy it will be to switch or transfer the data to another tool if the current runs out of maintenance?)
- Version control (e.g., can I track changes and revert to previous versions?)

Electronic lab notebooks (ELNs)

There is a very complete section with information and resources that will help selecting a ELN suitable to your needs [The Turing Way - Electronic Lab Notebooks](#). We highlight the following resources:

- Article detailing considerations for choosing ELN Higgins (2003).
- Comparison matrix of ELNs Harvard Longwood Medical Area Research Data Management Working Group (2021) (spreadsheet version [here](#)).
- ELN finder [online tool](#).

Consider that also tools not specifically designed as ELNs can have similar functionalities.

9.2.3 Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) and lab protocols

SOPs and lab protocols are essential to ensure that data collection has been implemented according to good practices, in a reliable manner. They can also be used to introduce new researchers in a project, facilitating collaboration. They are also key to reproducing and replicating experiments. For these reasons they constitute an important asset to share and publish. SOPs usually contain text and images. A recommended format is the standardized PDF (PDF/A-1 ISO 19005-1) which can be open with many software applications.

SOPs and protocols are often living documents that undergo relatively frequent changes and updates, thus requiring to keep track of the SOP versions.

They are necessary to comply with [Good Laboratory Practices](#).

Some examples of publicly available collections of SOPs:

- University of Zurich, Institute of Laboratory Animal Science, [SOPs](#)

- University of Michigan, animal care program [SOPs](#)
- John Hopkins University, research animal resources [SOPs](#)

9.3 Reporting guidelines: ARRIVE

A reporting guideline is a simple, structured tool for researchers to use while writing manuscripts. It provides a minimum list of information needed to ensure a manuscript can be understood, replicated, or used for a practical purpose or in a meta-analysis. You find more information on reporting guidelines in general at the [equator network](#).

The [ARRIVE](#) guidelines are a reporting guideline for **Animal Research: Reporting of *In Vivo* Experiments** are a checklist of recommendations for the full and transparent reporting of research involving animals (Percie Du Sert et al. 2020) . They are oriented to maximize quality and reliability of published research, therefore contributing to the 3R principles. These guidelines describe and give examples for the the following 10 essentials points (from ARRIVE Guidelines 2.0):

1. Study design

- 1a. The groups being compared, including control groups. If no control group has been used, the rationale should be stated
- 1b. The experimental unit (e.g., a single animal, litter, or cage of animals).

2. Sample size

- 2a. Specify the exact number of experimental units allocated to each group, and the total number in each experiment. Also indicate the total number of animals used.
- 2b. Explain how the sample size was decided. Provide details of any a priori sample size calculation, if done.

3. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

- 3a. Describe any criteria used for including or excluding animals (or experimental units) during the experiment, and data points during the analysis. Specify if these criteria were established a priori. If no criteria were set, state this explicitly.
- 3b. For each experimental group, report any animals, experimental units, or data points not included in the analysis and explain why. If there were no exclusions, state so.
- 3c. For each analysis, report the exact value of n in each experimental group.

4. **Randomisation**

4a. State whether randomisation was used to allocate experimental units to control and treatment groups. If done, provide the method used to generate the randomisation sequence.

4b. Describe the strategy used to minimise potential confounders such as the order of treatments and measurements, or animal/cage location. If confounders were not controlled, state this explicitly.

5. **Blinding**

Describe who was aware of the group allocation at the different stages of the experiment (during the allocation, the conduct of the experiment, the outcome assessment, and the data analysis).

6. **Outcome measures**

6a. Clearly define all outcome measures assessed (e.g., cell death, molecular markers, or behavioural changes).

6b. For hypothesis-testing studies, specify the primary outcome measure, i.e., the outcome measure that was used to determine the sample size.

7. **Statistical methods**

7a. Provide details of the statistical methods used for each analysis, including software used.

7b. Describe any methods used to assess whether the data met the assumptions of the statistical approach, and what was done if the assumptions were not met.

8. **Experimental animals**

8a. Provide species-appropriate details of the animals used, including species, strain and substrain, sex, age or developmental stage, and, if relevant, weight.

8b. Provide further relevant information on the provenance of animals, health/immune status, genetic modification status, genotype, and any previous procedures.

9. **Experimental procedures**

9a. What was done, how it was done, and what was used.

9b. When and how often.

9c. Where (including detail of any acclimatisation periods).

9d. Why (provide rationale for procedures).

10. **Results**

10a. Summary/descriptive statistics for each experimental group, with a measure of variability where applicable (e.g., mean and SD, or median and range).

10b. If applicable, the effect size with a confidence interval.

10 Tables and spreadsheets

Almost all research projects use some form of *tabular data*. They may contain descriptive information, experimental task performance, filenames of image or scan files, recording parameters, measurements or any other information for analysis. Further, *metadata tables* are also essential in a project as a form of structured metadata with essential information to interpret the data.

Guidelines for increasing the machine-readability of spreadsheets are given in (Perkel 2022) and (Broman and Woo 2018). We recommend these guidelines as they are concise and accessible reads. They highlight the need for consistency in formatting and machine-readability to enable automation of data validation, preprocessing, synthesis, and analysis of tabular data or metadata. Additional online material is provided in the chapter [data organisation in spreadsheets](#) of the e-book for reproducible research from ‘The Turing way’ (The Turing Way Community 2022). This page summarizes key points from the recommended guidelines and offers additional examples and information on common actions for working with tabular data.

10.1 Organizing tables or spreadsheets

Tables MUST be **structured** and **formatted** to be **machine-readable**. For example: do not encode any information with *formatting* (e.g., in color-coding schemes), but create additional columns instead that can be used as filter; do not merge cells and do not use empty cells (see examples below).

2. Use interoperable file formats

Publish and share them in an **interoperable** format, that is, a format compatible with most tools and programming languages. **Comma-separated values (.CSV)** is recommended. Working on spreadsheet software like MS Excel or Google Spreadsheets can be convenient and in some cases it may be preferred for collaborative editing of tabular data. When using such spreadsheet software, researchers should ensure that the table can be exported to more interoperable formats like CSV and read programmatically without losing or distorting the information.

3. Include a codebook or data dictionary

The tables MUST be shared/published together with a **codebook** or **data dictionary** that explains the meaning of the variables, abbreviations, naming conventions and units. This can be documented in a table format (e.g., variable names as rows in the first column and description in a second column) or in text format (e.g., in a README file).

4. Keep data 'tidy'

- Include a **single piece of information in a cell** (e.g., ,instead of a cell in the column `weight_20_kg` better make an entry 20 in a column `weight_kg`). More on tidy data in Wickham (2014).
- Keep formatting and naming **consistent** and follow broadly established **standards** when possible (e.g., write dates following ISO 8601 standard YYYY-MM-DD (this should be described in the data dictionary). There can be also standards referring to file or variable naming, units or number formats among others.

5. Keep raw data

Researchers may want to use functions in spreadsheet software or manual transformations to change the source data into more reusable format. If such transformations are necessary, at a minimum, keep track of them (document in a README file and/or share the script if there is one available) and make sure the results are read correctly when the files are exported into more interoperable formats like .CSV. Always keep the unedited raw data for future reference.

Examples

A poorly formatted table

The example in Table 10.1 illustrates errors that are often found in tables, specially when they are edited by multiple researchers . The structure is not adequate for data processing or analysis and there are inconsistencies in the cell values (e.g., subject labels) and formats (e.g., dates, decimals in weight). White spaces in variable names led to automatically adding a dot '.' when reading the table with R code. Color code seems to highlight images with artifacts.

Table 10.1: A poorly formatted table

Scanner	Subject ID	Scan_Date	Modality	Sex	Age (years)	Weight_kg	Experimental Group	Notes
Siemens								
	S01	01/01/2023	MRI	M	25	70	Ctrl	
	S002	01/02/2023	fMRI	F	26	72.04	Exp	Motion artifact
	S005	Feb 5, 2023	MRI	M		NA	Exp	Blurring
	S008	08/01/2023	T1	M	60	90	Exp	NA
Philips								
	sub003	03/01/2023	DTI	Male	27	75	Exp	High noise
	S006	06/01/2023	fMRI	F	30	82kg	Control	
	S009		MRI	F	33		Control	
GE								
	S004	04/01/2023	T1	Female	28	80	Control	Good scan
	S007	07/01/2023	DTI	NA	31	85	Exp	Strong signal
	S010	10/01/2023	fMRI	Male	34	N/A	Exp	

Table 10.2: A table formatted for machine-readability

Subject_ID	Scan_Date	Modality	Sex	Age_years	Weight_kg	Exp_Group	Scanner_Model	Discard	Notes
S001	01/01/2023	MRI	M	25	70	Control	Siemens	FALSE	None
S002	02/01/2023	fMRI	F	26	72.04	Exp	Siemens	TRUE	Motion artifact
S003	03/01/2023	DTI	M	27	75	Exp	Philips	TRUE	High noise
S004	04/01/2023	T1	F	28	80	Control	GE	FALSE	None
S005	05/01/2023	MRI	M	29	82	Exp	Siemens	FALSE	Good scan
S006	06/01/2023	fMRI	F	30	85	Control	Philips	TRUE	Blurring
S007	07/01/2023	DTI	NA	31	88	Exp	GE	FALSE	None
S008	08/01/2023	T1	F	32	90	Exp	Siemens	FALSE	Strong signal
S009	NA	MRI	M	33	92	Control	Philips	FALSE	None
S010	10/01/2023	fMRI	F	34	95	Exp	GE	FALSE	None

A better formatted version

The example in Table 10.2 can be easily read using code, **without ambiguities**. It is accompanied by a codebook (Table 10.3) describing the variables.

10.2 Frequent actions with tables

Researchers often need to do some minor transformations or operations with tabular data. The main recommendations are:

- Use **code** as it will be a more reproducible and transparent process than doing it manually. Irrespective of the programming language, the code for these operations is usually easy to implement for users without advance programming skills. In the R language, `dplyr` and `tidyr` are two useful packages for handling and manipulating tables.
- Keep the code and preferably keep track of changes in the code and the tables: **version control**.

Table 10.3: Example of a codebook

Variable	Description
Subject_ID	Unique subject identifier. Possible values: S001, S002, S010, etc.
Scan_Date	Date when the scan was performed. Possible values: YYYY-MM-DD.
Modality	Imaging modality used. Possible values: MRI, fMRI, DTI, or T1.
Sex	Biological sex of the subject. Possible values: M (male), F (female).
Age_years	Age of the subject in years. Possible values: 25, 30, 34.
Weight_kg	Subject's weight in kilograms. Possible values: e.g., 10.00.
Exp_Group	Experimental group assignment. Possible values: Control, Exp (experimental).
Scanner_Model	MRI scanner brand. Possible values: Siemens, Philips, or GE Discovery.
Discard	Discard images with artifacts TRUE or FALSE.
Notes	Additional notes on scan quality or issues. Possible values: Free text.

Data validation

There are a few initial checks and data validation actions that be conducted before archiving, publishing, sharing or conducting any analysis on tabular data to ensure they do not contain errors. Some frequent checks are:

- Variable types (e.g., numeric or character) and variable names (do they conform with the documented naming convention and codebook?)
- Missing values and complete cases (e.g., are they as expected?)
- Number and/or date formats (e.g., are they consistent?)
- Unique values (e.g., is sex consistently described with the same label?)
- Implausible values (e.g., negative age value, percentiles above 100)
- The ‘tail’ of the data (e.g., researchers may have calculated the mean of a column in the last row)

Some useful functions in **R** programming language are:

- `str()` (shows the structure of the data, including variable types and lengths)
- `unique()` (for unique values)
- `is.na()` (for missing values)
- `summary()` (summary statistics).

There are also dedicated packages for data validation. For a more detailed guideline, together with the code (in R) to perform different data validation actions we recommend the cookbook from the [validate package for R](#). For python users, a recent package for data validation is the [pointblank python package](#).

For a more conceptual overview, without code, we recommend the summary tables in the *framework for initial data analysis* (Huebner et al. 2018) used in the working group 3 from the [STRATOS initiative](#) (STRengthening Analytical Thinking for Observational Studies).

Combining tables

Researchers often need to combine information from two tables. A common scenario is to have a table with as many rows as subjects (e.g., subject characteristics) and another table with multiple rows per subject (e.g., indicating image files, slices, scans, etc.). If we want to merge these two tables we need a **key variable** that is consistent in both tables, for example, a `subjectID` variable uniquely identifying each subject. Here it is essential that each subject is labeled *consistently* and that the key variables have identical names in each table. A code example for this action can be found in the [Appendix Code Examples](#).

Reshaping tables: wide and long formats

We can distinguish two basic data formats:

- **Wide format:** values that do not repeat are usually in the first column and every measure that varies occupies a set of columns. E.g., One row per subject, columns specifying features of the subjects.
- **Long format:** multiple records for each individual. Some variables may not vary are identical in each record, whereas other variables vary across the records. E.g., Multiple rows per subject, listing filenames of images associated with each.

Research projects often need to combine both types of tables, and some statistical analysis or visualizations may required one specific table format. Researchers often need to ‘reshape’ the tables. An example of some easy code for this transformation can be seen in the [Appendix Code Examples](#). These transformations can become quite complex when manipulating large tables with many variables involved. **Always** check the output of these operations (e.g., running validation or descriptive summaries) to make sure that no information was misplaced or data was lost.

Table 10.5: Table converted to long format

Table 10.4: A table in wide format

Subject_ID	Test_A	Test_B
S001	5.4	3.2
S002	6.1	5.8
S003	7.3	6.5
S004	4.8	4.1

Subject_ID	Test	Value
S001	Test_A	5.4
S001	Test_B	3.2
S002	Test_A	6.1
S002	Test_B	5.8
S003	Test_A	7.3
S003	Test_B	6.5
S004	Test_A	4.8
S004	Test_B	4.1

11 Metadata companion files

Metadata are **essential information about data**. It is as important as the data itself, it provides the context to the data. Metadata include documents intended for human use, consisting mainly of text and images, but mostly, when referring to metadata we refer to **machine-readable information** in the form of tables (see [tables](#)) and **structured files that accompany data**. ‘Machine-readable’ means that it can be easily processed by computers without human intervention. These files are also referred sometimes as ‘sidecar’ or ‘companion’ files.

We recommend thinking about content and format of these files early on in a project. When possible, it is preferable to adopt or adjust discipline-specific standards (see [standards](#)) instead of creating new standards.

11.1 Format: JavaScript Object Notation (JSON)

A popular format for metadata companion files is [JavaScript Object Notation \(JSON\)](#). JSON is an open and text-based standard format for data interchange. It is often recommended as a format for metadata files because it is easy to read by humans and by many programming languages. JSON is also a good format for larger (metadata) data that have a **hierarchical structured relationship**. The structure of a JSON object is:

- The data are in name/value pairs and data objects are separated by commas
- Curly braces {} hold objects
- Square brackets [] hold arrays
- Each data element is enclosed with quotes “ ” if it is a character, or without quotes if it is a numeric value

The ‘fields’ or name and value pairs in the JSON files can vary widely depending on the data and file type they are accompanying. The examples are provided by the [Brain Imaging Data Standards](#) for microscopy data:

Example of sidecar JSON file (*_<suffix>.json)

```
{
  "Manufacturer": "Hamamatsu",
  "ManufacturersModelName": "C9600-12",
  "PixelSize": [0.23, 0.23],
  "PixelSizeUnits": "um",
  "Magnification": 40,
  "BodyPart": "BRAIN",
  "BodyPartDetails": "corpus callosum",
  "SampleEnvironment": "ex vivo",
  "SampleFixation": "4% paraformaldehyde, 2% glutaraldehyde",
  "SampleStaining": "LFB",
  "SliceThickness": 5,
  "TissueDeformationScaling": 97
}
```

Example of participants.json:

```
{
  "species": {
    "Description": "binomial species name from the NCBI Taxonomy  
(https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Taxonomy/Browser/wwwtax.cgi)"
  },
  "strain": {
    "Description": "name of the strain of the species"
  },
  "strain_rrid": {
    "Description": "research resource identifier (RRID) of the strain  
(https://rrid.site/data/source/nlx\_154697-1/search)"
  }
}
```

11.2 Creating metadata files from tables

Data acquisition instruments often generate metadata files automatically. However, this is not always the case and sometimes researchers need to customize the content of these files. Adopting existing metadata [standards](#) is usually recommended. Some projects may require their own [JSON-schemas](#), although developing these schema may be labor intensive and require data stewards or expert data managers. Often, simpler solutions are sufficient, and researchers may, for example, generate a JSON file from the content of a table (see Table 11.1). This can be done using many programming languages, for

example, the R package [jsonlite](#) is simple to use and offers several encoding formatting options. Automatically generating these files is recommended, rather than resorting to manual edits that can lead to errors that go unnoticed. An example of R code to create a JSON file from a table is provided in [Appendix Code Examples](#).

Table 11.1: Example of metadata in tabular format.

id	img_location	sex	condition	treatment
subject_04	dummyfolder/subject_04_imgfile.tiff	female	A	control
subject_93	dummyfolder/subject_93_imgfile.tiff	female	B	control
subject_12	dummyfolder/subject_12_imgfile.tiff	female	B	treat_3
subject_65	dummyfolder/subject_65_imgfile.tiff	male	B	control
subject_98	dummyfolder/subject_98_imgfile.tiff	female	A	treat_1
subject_71	dummyfolder/subject_71_imgfile.tiff	male	A	treat_3
subject_24	dummyfolder/subject_24_imgfile.tiff	female	B	control

The first row of Table 11.1 can be represented in a JSON file would look like this:

```
{
  "id": "subject_04",
  "img_location": "dummyfolder/subject_04_imgfile.tiff",
  "sex": "female",
  "condition": "A",
  "treatment": "control"
}
```

12 Controlled vocabularies and ontologies

For data to be reusable, the metadata and documentation must use consistent terminology that is clearly explained so that different users can understand its meaning unambiguously. We recommend starting with simple, controlled vocabularies before moving on to more complex structures, such as taxonomies or ontologies. As with other metadata and documentation elements, standard or widely used vocabularies or ontologies should be used where available.

12.1 Controlled vocabularies

Controlled vocabularies are standardized and organized arrangements of words and phrases presented as alphabetical lists of terms or as thesauri and taxonomies with a hierarchical structure of broader and narrower terms ([see ‘controlled vocabulary’ concept in EU vocabulary](#)).

- **Consistency:** they provide a common language for researchers, minimizing variations and ambiguities
- **Interoperability:** they facilitate integration and sharing of data across systems, disciplines, and organizations, enabling seamless collaboration (human and machine actionable).
- **Reusability:** Research data annotated with standard vocabularies are easier to interpret and reuse

12.2 Taxonomies

A taxonomy is a controlled vocabulary in which all the terms belong to a single hierarchical structure and have parent/child or broader/narrower relationships to other terms. The structure is sometimes referred to as a ‘tree’. The addition of non-preferred terms/synonyms may or may not be part of a taxonomy. ([see ‘taxonomy’ concept in EU vocabularies](#)).

12.3 Ontologies

An ontology is a formal way of representing knowledge about a specific domain, using a structured framework of concepts and their relationships [see ‘ontology’ in EU vocabularies](#). It can also be seen as a hierarchical graph covering a specific subject area or domain. An ontology has classes (i.e., concepts, terms, etc) as basic units and relations or inks between the classes.

12.4 Selected resources

- [Open Biological and Biomedical Ontology Foundry](#) is a community that develops interoperable ontologies for the biological sciences
- [Ontobee](#) is a server that aims to facilitate ontology data sharing, visualization, query integration and analysis.
- [FairSharing](#) is a platform to look for standards, policies and databases. It can also be used to search for ontologies and controlled vocabularies

Part III

Archiving, Sharing and Publishing

13 File formats

The choice of a format will determine how data can be accessed throughout its lifecycle, including sharing and reuse. In general, we need to consider **long-term preservation** when choosing a format. Files in formats with the following features will be more likely to be accessible in the future:

- Non-proprietary
- Open, documented standard
- Popular format
- Standard representation
- Unencrypted
- Uncompressed

We recommend selecting file formats based on these features and to follow existing guidelines for general and domain-specific file formats. The section below summarizes the file formats recommended by various institutions.

13.1 File formats in the general domain

There are many institutions providing recommendations on file formats in general. This section shows a couple of representative examples.

Recommendations from the Faculty of Biology and Medicine, University of Lausanne ([Medical Library](#)):

Category	Recommended Formats
Text	PDF/A – PDF/X, Plain text (.txt), Open Office (.odt), XML / HTML (with schema), Word XML (.docx), RTF, LaTeX
Images	Bitmap: TIFF (uncompressed), PNG, JPEG2000, (GIF). Vector: SVG

Category	Recommended Formats
Tabular Data	CSV (comma, tab, semi-colon), Open Office (.ods), XML / HTML (with schema), Excel (.xlsx), .SQL
Video	MPEG-4 (H.264) (~ MP4), Motion JPEG 2000, MPEG-1/2
Audio	WAV (preferably Broadcast Wave Format, LPCM), AIFF (LPCM), OGG Vorbis, MP3 (MPEG Layer III), AAC (MPEG-4)

Recommendations from the open data publishing platform ([Dryad](#)):

Category	Recommended formats
README files	Markdown (<i>MD</i>) or text (<i>TXT</i>)
Tabular data	Comma-separated values (<i>CSV</i>)
Non-tabular data	Semi-structured plain text (e.g., protein sequences)
Structured plain text	<i>XML</i> , <i>JSON</i> (e.g., metadata companion files)
Images	<i>PDF</i> , <i>JPEG</i> , <i>PNG</i> , <i>TIFF</i> , <i>SVG</i>
Audio	<i>FLAC</i> , <i>AIFF</i> , <i>WAV</i> , <i>MP3</i> , <i>OGG</i>
Video	<i>AVI</i> , <i>MPEG</i> , <i>MP4</i>
Compressed file archives	<i>TAR.GZ</i> , <i>7Z</i> , <i>ZIP</i>

13.2 Interoperable formats in neuroimaging

There are many modalities of neuroimaging research and therefore many different file formats used in this field. This section covers some of the most popular formats in neuroimaging. The [Brain Imaging Data Structure - BIDS](#) standards also provides recommendations for some of these formats in the different data modalities available.

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), Computed Tomography (CT), Positron Emission Tomography (PET) and similar

- Neuroimaging Informatics Technology Initiative ([NIFTI](#)). It is an open file format commonly used to store imaging data obtained with magnetic resonance imaging methods. The associated file extensions are: *.nii*, *.nii.gz*, *.hdr/.img*.
- Digital Imaging and Communication in Medicine ([DICOM](#)) is a technical standard for digital storage and transmission of biomedical images. It was developed in the

80s and it is widely in use today. The DICOM standard is widely adopted by hospitals and medical software. The files extension is usually `.dcm`.

Microscopy

- OME data model. OME Model is an specification from the Open Microscopy Environment for storing data on biological imaging. The model includes parameter and extensive metadata. **OME-XML** is a file format used to store data according ot the model. **OME-TIFF** is a multiplane tiff file with OME metadata in the header (as OME-XML). See more details in their publication (Goldberg et al. 2005). Further, **OME-ZARR** (sometimes referred to as OME-NGFF or NGFF) is a cloud-optimized format developed to improve access and storage for large data (Moore et al. 2023).
- In BIDS ([v1.10.0](#)) microscopy raw data MUST be stored in one of the following formats:
 - [Portable Network Graphics \(.png\)](#)
 - [Tag Image File Format \(.tif\)](#)
 - [OME-TIFF \(.ome.tif for standard TIFF files or .ome.btf for BigTIFF files\)](#)
 - [OME-ZARR/NGFF \(.ome.zarr directories\)](#)

Electroencephalography (EEG) and intracranial electroencephalography (iEEG)

There is no single standard. The recommendations from BIDS for raw data are the following:

- [European data format \(.edf\)](#). Each recording is a single file. `edf+` files are permitted. The capital `.EDF` extension MUST NOT be used.
- [BrainVision Core Data Format \(.vhdr, .vmrk, .eeg\)](#). Each dataset recording consists of a file triplet.
- [EEGLAB \(.set, .fdt\)](#). The format used by the MATLAB toolbox EEGLAB. Each recording consists of a `.set` file with an OPTIONAL `.fdt` file.
- [Neurodata Without Borders \(.nwb\)](#). For iEEG data only. Each recording consists of a single `.nwb` file.
- [MEF3 \(.mefd\)](#). For iEEG data only. Each recording consists of a `.mefd` directory.
- [Biosemi \(.bdf\)](#). For EEG data only. Each recording consists of a single `.bdf` file. `bdf+` files are permitted. The capital `.BDF` extension MUST NOT be used.

13.3 Metadata, markup and data serialization

For more information about metadata see the section [Metadata companion files](#). Markup languages specify the structure and formatting of a document. Data serialization languages are used to create configuration files in plain text and compatible between systems.

- [JavaScript Object Notation \(JSON\)](#) (`.json`) In the BIDS specification, JSON files are primarily used as “sidecar” files accompanying the data files. There are also a few special cases of JSON files being first-order data files, such as `genetic_info.json`.
- [Extensible Markup Language \(XML\)](#) (`.xml`) is a markup language and file format for storing, transmitting, and reconstructing data.
- [YAML Ain’t Markup Language](#) (`.yaml`, `.yml`) is a human-friendly data serialization language for all programming languages which is often used for configuration files.
- [Markdown](#), a lightweight language with simple syntax that will add formatting elements to plain text. This format is widely used for technical documentation online.

13.4 File format conversion

There are multiple reasons why researchers often have to convert files to a different format. For example, imaging acquisition hardware may generate files in a proprietary format. Researchers will often convert these files to a standardized format like NIFTI to be able to analyze it, share and publish the images in a ‘more universally’ interoperable format. File compression is also often done to facilitate sharing.

These are some important considerations when converting files:

- Quality should be preserved: there should be no data loss (e.g., lossy compression methods where some data is lost may have an impact when reusing the data) or data corruption (data that is still present but unreadable).
- When possible, the source and converted files should be kept, in case errors in the process were to be found in the future.
- Conversion is better done automatically with a script logging any conversion parameters.
- Long-time preservation and reusability should be considered when choosing the conversion format.

14 Version control

Version control refers to the **record of changes** made in a file or set of files over time. The record should allow collaborators to **track history**, to **review** and to **revert** changes. Versioning refers to the management of changes in a file or project (read more in <https://book.the-turing-way.org/reproducible-research/vcs>).

Versioning is very important for **scientific reproducibility** and **transparency** as it allows to follow **provenance information**, i.e., the record of how the results are derived from data. Data and code evolve and change over time and it can become really difficult to track which version of them generated a figure or a results table in a publication.

We recommend adopting Git, introduced below, to apply version control in documents, data and code. We suggest beginning with simple workflows; there is no need to master all of Git's advanced features right away.

14.1 Version control in documents

There are many tools widely used tools for version control and collaborative editing of text documents. For example, MS Word, Google Docs and Overleaf. These tools have some limitations that need to be considered:

- They require a master document (a single source document where we edit changes)
- It does not scale up well to large number of collaborators
- These tools do not show the complete history of changes
- The changes and master document are stored in a company's cloud
- They only work for specific types of documents

In view of these limitations, these tools cannot provide a reliable and manageable version control system for many research outputs like metadata, documentation, tables and specially code.

14.2 Git version control system for data science

Git is a version control system that tracks changes in files, including timestamps. It is the *de facto standard in code development* and it is increasingly used in research and data science in general. It is **open source**, developed by Linus Torvalds in 2005. These are some characteristics of the Git system:

- It is known to be fast, efficient, and reliable
- Runs on all major operating systems
- it is integrated in most IDEs (Integrated Development Environments): RStudio, Visual Studio Code, Eclipse, PyCharm, Spyder, MATLAB@...

Git is a **distributed version control system (DVCS)**, which means collaborators create local copies of a project, make changes locally and then commit those changes to a remote repository (see Figure 14.1)

Figure 14.1: Centralized vs distributed version control systems

14.2.1 Main concepts in Git

- **Repository:** A collection of files, typically organized as a project, managed with version control.
- **Commit:** The action of recording changes in a repository. It is like a snapshot of the entire repository at a given time.

- **History:** A registry (“log”) and collection of all the snapshots (“commits”) of a repository, allowing us to revert changes.

14.2.2 Platforms to host Git repositories online

- **GitLab:** An open-source web-based tool that provides a Git repository manager (www.gitlab.com). Many institutions and organizations have their own GitLab instance (e.g., UZH <https://gitlab.uzh.ch/>).
- **GitHub:** Another provider, owned by Microsoft (potential data governance issues) (www.github.com).

14.2.3 An overview of the Git system

The main areas and commands in Git are summarized in Figure 14.2.

Git ‘areas’:

- **Remote repository:** the online repository with all files and history of changes, hosted in platforms like Gitlab or Github.
- **Workspace:** this is the “visible” folder. In most cases this is a local folder with a copy of the online repository (including history of changes).
- **Index :** (not directly visible) is a staging area used to prepare changes before committing them to the project history
- **Local repository:** (usually a hidden folder `.git`) is a copy of the entire project’s history and codebase

Main actions:

- **Pull:** Pull changes from the remote to update the local copy.
- **Commit & Push:** Commit and push local changes into the remote.
- **Revert:** Revert changes to a previous commit.

Git Data Transport Commands

<http://osteele.com>

Figure 14.2: Overview of Git commands

Workflows

Git can be used in the context of complex application development and in smaller settings. Although there may be a steep learning curve at the beginning, scientists can gradually incorporate Git into their routine workflow and it can be kept relatively simple without needing to use all the advanced features.

- **Branches:** a repository can have multiple ‘branches’, which allows working in parallel. The same user or multiple collaborators can work on parallel versions of the repository. Some of the changes from the branches (e.g., new features into the main code) can be eventually merged into the ‘main’ code branch.

Figure 14.3: Illustration of git branches from [the Turing Way](#)

Publishing and sharing

- **Releases.** The content of a Git repository is changing frequently. When scientists publish the code associated with a publication, the version of the repository with the files involved in that published analysis need to be also shared. That can be done by publishing a gitlab release, which is a *snapshot* of a repository with a version *tag*.
- **Persistent identifiers.** Sharing the URL to a Gitlab or Github repository associated with a publication is not recommended. The URL may change in time and the code version become unavailable. It is recommended to publish a Git repository *release* in a platform that allows to assign a persistent identifier. For example, a **digital object identifier or DOI**, so that the repository can become a citable resource to be found in the future. Platforms like Zenodo, for example, offer direct integration with Github, assigning a DOI to every release of the repository. Another way is to simply upload in the platform a *.zip* folder with all the files in the repository (the ‘snapshot’ created when making a release) with a version tag.

Best practices

Setting up a repository

- “Documentation is a love letter that you write to your future self.”
- Add a README file in the main folder (root folder) and in other folders if needed.
- Use a **naming convention** with a balance between concise and informative names. Avoid too cryptic or ambiguous folder or file names. For example: `run_model_AB.r` instead of `run_scripts.r`

Code writing

- Consider **numbering scripts** that need to be run sequentially.
- Use **relative paths**.
- Log **software libraries** and **system dependencies**, e.g., `sessionInfo()`, and hardware when applicable.
- Scripts should include **comments** (but concise).
- Consider scripts to generate **reports** (dynamic reporting).

Sharing and Publishing

- **Describe the project** in the main README file (dates, project ID, funding, affiliations, and DOI).
- When the repository contains the code associated with a publication, include the DOI of the publication in the main README file.
- Create a **release**, take a snapshot with a version tag .
- Assign a **DOI** to the release.
- Include a **license file** to explain reusability (agree with PI, e.g., GPL, MIT).
- Specify the location of the source data.

14.3 Selected resources

- Article on Git and reproducibility and transparency in science: Ram (2013): <https://doi.org/10.1186/1751-0473-8-7>.
- Primer on digital collaboration from the Center for Reproducible Hofmann et al. (2023): <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8354375>.
- Reproducibility in Practice: Version Control and Dynamic Reporting - workshop materials Fraga Gonzalez (n.d.): <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14754696>.

15 Archives and online repositories

Making research data available to others for reuse is essential to scientific progress and the main purpose of archiving open research data (ORD). This is recognized in the [funding regulations](#) of the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF).

We recommend to plan early for the archiving of research outputs — deciding what will be archived, how, when, and where. At a minimum, a data archive should involve raw data as well as any relevant derivatives, metadata files and documentation, and when applicable, any code involved in processing the data or making it usable. Without the adequate context, provided by metadata and documentation, archiving data results in a data dump of little scientific value.

15.1 Types of data archives

15.1.1 Data temperature by frequency of access

We can broadly classify the data archives by how frequently we expect it be accessed. Table 15.1 summarizes different ‘temperatures’ of the data defined by access frequency (Pernet et al. 2023). Irrespective of the *temperature*, any data archiving should comply with the pertinent legal governance requirements. The contents and steps described in this primer can apply to any type of archive, but the presented use-case fits into the warm archive category. It should be noted that an archive does not necessarily make data publicly available immediately and most repositories allow restricting access, for example by requiring an application or applying an embargo until a publication is released.

Table 15.1: An overview of different types of data archives depending on the frequency of access.

Feature \ Temperature	Cold	Warm	Hot
Access frequency	Very low	Regular	Constant
Back-ups	No	Yes	Yes
Costs	Cheap	Expensive	Expensive
Content	All	High-utility	High-utility
Duration	Long	Long	Short/Medium
Medium	Tape	Disk/Server/Cloud	Disk/Server/Cloud

Feature \ Temperature	Cold	Warm	Hot
Online	No	Yes	Yes

- **Cold** data are not expected to be accessed in a long time but they should still be curated, unlike data considered *disposable* (Pernet et al. 2023). In some contexts, rarely accessed data can be essential. Collecting new data is usually much more expensive than archiving existing data, so it is generally advisable to cold-archive everything by default. Tapes are relatively cheap and robust to data quality deterioration if stored in facilities that ensure data integrity preservation. Cold data tends to involve larger storage volume than warm and hot data, as it includes all data, including that of limited utility. Therefore it is often not cost-effective to make cold data available online.
- **Warm** data are expected to be accessed regularly and they are long-term archived in online servers or cloud repositories. Usually there are multiple back-up copies in physically separated locations to protect data integrity. Warm data are considered of high-utility for research reuse.
- **Hot** data are accessed constantly for a specific period of time, for example, while a project is running to share it with collaborators. Hot data are stored in relatively expensive online servers or cloud repositories, and are more likely to move location than cold and warm data.

15.2 Open Research Data (ORD) online repositories

Open research data repositories aim at preserving and making data freely accessible to anyone, promoting transparency and scientific collaboration. Online repositories are meant to host *warm* data that will be accessed. They are too expensive and not conceived for storing *cold* data that will remain for long time without being used. Nonetheless, a good online repository should offer security and guaranty that the data will be findable and accessible for a long period of time.

15.2.1 SNSF requirements and FAIR repositories

A key requirement in a repository is that it should provide a persistent identifier to the data and metadata and facilitate making the archived data “**FAIR enough**”. These can be determining factors when evaluating the suitability of a repository, although assessing its FAIRness may not be a straightforward task. For example, the Swiss National Science Foundation defined a set of minimal criteria for the repositories to fulfill to be considered as ‘FAIR enough’ (Milzow et al. 2020). The **criteria** in that report were:

- Globally unique and persistent identifiers are attributed to data sets (e.g. DOI)

- Upload of intrinsic (e.g. author’s name, content of dataset, associated publication, etc.) and submitter-defined (e.g. definition of variable names, etc.) metadata possible
- Reuse defined (e.g. Creative Commons, Open Data Commons, etc.)
- Citation information and metadata always (even in the case of datasets with restricted access) publicly accessible
- Intrinsic metadata submitted via standardized template/mask (to ensure machine readability and interoperability)
- Long-term preservation plan for the archived data in place

Initiatives like the [CoreTrustSeal](#) make these criteria more explicit by defining and providing certifications based on how well repositories can ensure long-term storage and accessibility of data. These certifications also try to integrate FAIR-enabling assessments, taking into account repository features that help publishing FAIRer data.

15.2.2 Finding a repository

The [SNSF requires](#) researchers to submit data associated with the project’s publications into public repositories. Researchers are therefore encouraged to think about the field-specific options available in the early stages of project planning:

- The SNSF provides an [overview of data repositories](#) and links to relevant institutional, generalist and discipline-specific repositories.
- The website <https://www.re3data.org/>, (Pampel et al. 2013) also listed on the SNSF page, allows to explore the available options for a variety of domains. This data base allows browsing by subject, content type and country, as well as other filters (e.g., versioning, metadata standards, data licenses and many others).

15.2.3 Popular generalist repositories

- [Open Science Framework \(OSF\)](#). OSF is a free and open-source software platform to facilitate open collaboration. It is multidisciplinary, besides DOIs, it offers synchronization with Git platforms and it has its own platform for preprints and study registrations. The default storage location is the United States, but it allows to choose other locations from those available, including Canada, Germany, and Australia.
- [Zenodo](#). Zenodo is an Open Science platform built and developed by researchers. Hosted, developed, and operated by OpenAIRE and CERN (Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire) scientists. It is free and accommodates any type of

research data. It offers DOI versioning and good direct integration with Github. It also offers the possibility of creating communities.

15.2.4 Repositories of special interest for preclinical neuroimaging

- [EBRAINS](#). EBRAINS is a platform and repository created as a core aim of the EU-funded Human Brain Project to promote advancements in scientific and industrial research in neuroscience, computing, and brain-related medicine. It gathers a broad range of data and tools, including computing resources. It is designed to accommodate large volumes of data. The platform offers EBRAIN Curation Services accessible via a request form.
- [Image Data Resource \(IDR\)](#) is a public repository of reference (microscopy) image datasets from published studies. It is led by PIs from Dundee University and the European Molecular Biology Laboratory - European Bioinformatics Institute. The accepted images must be *reference images* according to the criteria of the [Euro-BioImaging - Elixir Image Data Strategy](#). For other images, the IDR website points at project repositories of [BioStudies](#) and [Dryad](#). Metadata guidelines are provided together with examples and templates of annotations.
- [OpenNeuro](#). OpenNeuro is the former openfMRI repository, from which the Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS) guidelines emerged. It offers DOIs to dataset *snapshots* (versions) and although it has a strong focus on human neuroimaging, there are also animal imaging datasets published. It is focused exclusively on neuroimaging data of different modalities (MRI, PET, MEG, EEG, and iEEG). It is free, maintained by the Stanford Center for Reproducible Neuroscience, and endorsed by NIH as a data-sharing resource.

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Part IV
Appendix

Glossary

Terms and abbreviations relevant to this project

Chapter 1: 3R principles

Guiding principles of animal experimentation

Replacement

Methods that achieve a purpose without conducting experiments or procedures on animals

Reduction

Methods that obtain comparable information using fewer animals or maximize data collection from the same number of animals.

Refinement

Methods that minimize pain, suffering, and distress while enhancing animal well-being.

Chapter 2: Reproducibility

Definitions from National Academy of Science

Reproducibility or computational reproducibility

Obtaining consistent computational results using the same input data, computational steps, methods, code, and conditions of analysis.

Replicability

Obtaining consistent results across studies aimed at answering the same scientific question, each of which has obtained its own data.

Generalizability

The extent that results of a study apply in other contexts or populations that differ from the original one.

Chapter 3: Open Research Data

Research data

The actual records (such as numerical scores, textual records, images, and sounds) resulting from research that is partially or fully funded by public funds, used as primary sources for scientific research, and that are commonly accepted in the scientific community as necessary to validate research findings. This term does not cover laboratory notebooks, preliminary analyses, or drafts of scientific papers, plans for future research, peer reviews, personal communications with colleagues, or physical objects, (e.g., laboratory samples, strains of bacteria, or test animals).

Research Data Management (RDM)

The handling of research data (collection, organisation, storage, and documentation) during and after a research activity.

Open Research Data (ORD)

Data that can be freely accessed, reused, remixed and redistributed, for academic research and teaching purposes and beyond. Ideally, open data have no restrictions on reuse or redistribution, and are appropriately licensed as such.

Chapter 4: Preregistration

Preregistration

A publication of research plan (hypotheses, methods, analyses) before an study is conducted.

Registered reports

A publication involving a two-stage peer review process where a study proposal is reviewed before data collection and the final manuscript is reviewed after analysis. At stage 1, researchers can obtain in-principle acceptance, so even if no statistically significant results are found in the planned analyses, the paper would be accepted for publication.

Peer community in registered reports (PCI-RR)

The PCI initiative is a researcher-run initiative that publishes peer-reviews of preprints and the PCI-RR community is dedicated to receiving, reviewing and recommending registered reports across disciplines.

Chapter 5: The FAIR principles

Guiding principles for guiding the management of digital resources, specifically scientific data and metadata.

Findable

It should be possible for others to discover your data. Rich metadata should be available online in a searchable resource, and the data should be assigned a persistent identifier.

Accessible

It should be possible for humans and machines to gain access to your data, under specific conditions or restrictions where appropriate. FAIR does not mean that data need to be open! There should be metadata, even if the data are not accessible.

Interoperable

Data and metadata should conform to recognized formats and standards to allow them to be combined and exchanged.

Reusable

Lots of documentation is needed to support data interpretation and reuse. The data should conform to community norms and be clearly licensed so others know what kinds of reuse are permitted.

Chapter 6: Data Management Plan

Data Management Plan (DMP)

A document required by SNSF grants that outlines a plan of the life cycle of the data. It includes data handling practices, ethical and legal issues, storage, and sharing plans. DMPs remain editable during the entire lifetime of the grant.

Chapter 7: legal & Ethical considerations

Animal Welfare Act

The [Art. 1 in conjunction with Art. 3 let.a](#) from The Federal Assembly of the Swiss Confederation aims to protect the dignity and welfare of animals.

The Ethics Committee for Animal Experimentation (ECAE)

The [ECAE](#) of the Swiss Academies has published an extensive guideline to help researchers carry out the weighing of interests for any proposed animal experiment ([2nd Edition from 2022](#)).

Chapter 8: Standards

Metadata and data organization standards

Community-specific descriptions of how to structure data, metadata, filenaming conventions and file formats.

Chapter 9: Documentation, protocols and reporting

Electronic lab notebooks (ELNs)

Software system designed to help researchers organize and store experimental procedures, protocols, plans, notes and data. ELNs are a digital version of the traditional paper notebooks most researchers kept in the lab during data collection. Ideally, a ELN will use open formats and enable version control.

Good Laboratory Practices (GLP)

Guidelines with the aim to ensure quality of the process and conditions under which studies are planned, performed, monitored, recorded, archived and reported.

README files

These are plain text files usually in .txt or Markdown (.md) format. They are intended mostly for humans rather than for machine-readability. README files typically describe the important information, written in a concise manner, to help understanding the content of a folder.

Reporting guidelines

Guidelines with recommendations and checklists to make reporting more complete and transparent, maximizing quality and reliability of published research.

Standard operating procedures (SOPs)

Detailed instructions or step-by-step guides describing how to conduct specific research, for example how to conduct an experiment or collect data. Their aim is to make specific research practices and settings consistent.

Chapter 10: Tables and spreadsheets

Comma-separated values (CSV)

A text file format using commas to separate values and newlines(`\r\n` in Windows and `\n` in Mac and Linux) to separate rows or records. It is a format preferred for interoperability over spreadsheet file formats like .xls. An alternative is tab-separated values (TSV) files.

Codebook

In the context of tables and spreadsheets, a codebook is a table or text file describing the variable names from a table or spreadsheet, and their meanings.

Chapter 11: Metadata companion files

Metadata

Metadata refers to information about digital objects, in this case, about research data. It is as important as the data, as without metadata we cannot find, interpret or use the data. Metadata can be structured, machine-readable files (e.g., .JSON or .XML) or tables (e.g., .csv) or unstructured text (e.g., README files) and documentation aimed at human readers.

Metadata companion files

Are structured files with metadata that accompany data files, providing with machine-readable information about the data files. They are also call sometimes 'sidecar' files.

JavaScript Object Notation (JSON)

An open and text-based standard format for data interchange. It is often recommended as a format for metadata files because it is easy to read by humans and by many programming languages. JSON is also a good format for larger (metadata) data that have a hierarchical structured relationship. The JSON structure has name/value pairs separated by commas.

Chapter 12: Controlled vocabularies and ontologies

Controlled vocabulary

standardized and organized arrangement of words and phrases presented as alphabetical lists of terms or as thesauri and taxonomies with a hierarchical structure of broader and narrower terms.

Ontology

An ontology is a formal way of representing knowledge about a specific domain, using a structured framework of concepts and their relationships. A hierarchical graph covering a specific subject area or domain.

Taxonomy

a controlled vocabulary in which all the terms belong to a single hierarchical structure and have parent/child or broader/narrower relationships to other terms. The structure is sometimes referred to as a tree.

Chapter 13: File formats

Interoperability

Interoperability refers to how well data (and metadata) can be shared and reused across systems, disciplines and organization. Open formats have better interoperability and are less prone to obsolescence.

Chapter 14: Version Control

Git

Git is a free and open source distributed version control system designed to handle everything from small to very large projects with speed and efficiency. Git allows to tracks change in files, including timestamps and to revert changes. It is the *de facto* standard for version control in code development.

Version control

Version control refers to the record of changes made in a file or set of files over time. The record should allow collaborators to track history , review and revert changes.

Versioning

The management of changes in a file or project

Chapter 15: Archives and online repositories

Archiving

Data archiving usually refers to long-term storage and preservation of the data.

Cold data archive

Refers to archiving data not expected to be accessed in a long time but that can still be considered important and should still be curated, unlike data considered disposable. Cold data tends to involve larger storage volume than warm and hot data, as it includes all data, including that of limited utility. Tapes are relatively cheap and robust to data quality deterioration if stored in facilities that ensure data integrity preservation.

Warm data archive

Refers to archiving data expected to be accessed regularly, long-term archived in online servers or cloud repositories. Usually there are multiple back-up copies in physically separated locations to protect data integrity. Warm data are considered of high-utility for research reuse.

Hot data archive or storage

Refers to storage of data that are accessed constantly for a specific period of time, for example, while a project is running to share it with collaborators. Hot data are stored in relatively expensive online servers or cloud repositories, and are more likely to move location than cold and warm data.

Repository

A technical infrastructure that stores data, ensures data integrity and makes them accessible in the long-term with appropriate services to manage content and metadata and access control.

R Code examples

R code snippets for table manipulation

In R language `dplyr` and `tidyr` are two useful packages for handling and manipulating tables.

R code snippet to join two tables

```
library(dplyr)

# Read csv tables
tbl_subjects <- read.csv('dummy_table_OK.csv')
tbl_files <- read.csv('dummy_table_filenames.csv')

# Join by variable "Subject_ID"
tbl_joined <- dplyr::full_join(x=tbl_subjects,
                              y = tbl_files,
                              by=join_by("Subject_ID"))
```

In more complex settings, it is possible to specify the expected relationship between two tables (e.g., if each row from table x is expected to have a match in table y, etc.) see [mutate-joins](#).

R code to convert from wide to long format

```
library(tidyr)
library(dplyr)

# Make an example table
tbl_wide <- data.frame(
  Subject_ID = c("S001", "S002", "S003", "S004"),
  Test_A = c(5.4, 6.1, 7.3, 4.8),
```

Table 15.2: Table with file information

Subject_ID	Files	Session
S001	filename1.ext	1
S002	NA	NA
S003	filename1.ext	1
S003	filename2.ext	1
S003	filename3.ext	2
S003	filename4.ext	2

Table 15.3: Combined table after adding subject information

Subject_ID	Scan_Date	Modality	Sex	Age_years	Weight_kg	Exp_Group	Scanner_Model	Notes	Files	Session
S001	01/01/2023	MRI	M	25	70.00	Control	Siemens	None	filename1.ext	1
S002	02/01/2023	fMRI	F	26	72.04	Exp	Siemens	Motion artifact	NA	NA
S003	03/01/2023	DTI	M	27	75.00	Exp	Philips	High noise	filename1.ext	1
S003	03/01/2023	DTI	M	27	75.00	Exp	Philips	High noise	filename2.ext	1
S003	03/01/2023	DTI	M	27	75.00	Exp	Philips	High noise	filename3.ext	2
S003	03/01/2023	DTI	M	27	75.00	Exp	Philips	High noise	filename4.ext	2

```

Test_B = c(3.2, 5.8, 6.5, 4.1)
)

# Convert to long format
tbl_long <- tbl_wide %>%
  pivot_longer(cols = c(Test_A, Test_B), names_to = "Test",
               values_to = "Value")

```

R code to convert from long to wide format

```

library(tidyr)
library(dplyr)

tbl_wide_again <- tbl_long %>%
  pivot_wider(names_from = Test, values_from = Value)

```

R code snippet to create JSON files from a table

In this example each row of a table with metadata is transformed into a JSON file. The R package [jsonlite](#) offers several encoding formatting options.

- A dummy metadata table

id	img_location	sex	condition	treatment
subject_04	dummyfolder/subject_04_imgfile.tiff	female	A	control
subject_93	dummyfolder/subject_93_imgfile.tiff	female	B	control
subject_12	dummyfolder/subject_12_imgfile.tiff	female	B	treat_3
subject_65	dummyfolder/subject_65_imgfile.tiff	male	B	control
subject_98	dummyfolder/subject_98_imgfile.tiff	female	A	treat_1
subject_71	dummyfolder/subject_71_imgfile.tiff	male	A	treat_3
subject_24	dummyfolder/subject_24_imgfile.tiff	female	B	control

- The rows converted to JSON

```
library(jsonlite)

# Write each row to a JSON object
row_json <- list()
for (i in 1:nrow(metadata_table)) {
  row_json[[i]] <- toJSON(metadata_table[i, ],
                           pretty = TRUE,
                           auto_unbox = TRUE)
}
```

The following line can be added in the loop to save the row as a JSON file with the same name as the images listed in the table

```
img_file_name <- basename(metadata_table$img_location[i])
json_file_name <- sub("\\.tiff$", ".json", img_file_name)
write(row_json[[i]], file = json_file_name)
```